

Risk-Based Criticality for Network Utilities Asset Management

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Abstract— This paper describes the design and the implementation of a process of asset criticality analysis for Distribution Network Services Providers (DNSP), also named Network Utilities. The proposed method is based on two points: (i) the elicitation of business-value factors, and (ii) the risk-based evaluation of assets, considering potential impacts of their failures on network value. Thus, it provides the capability to take maintenance management decision in terms of value and risk, considering the whole network under unique and homogeneous criteria. A hierarchy of assets ranked will come out of this process, which represents a fundamental result serving as input of the subsequent steps of the asset management process, including maintenance and renewal/reinvestments decisions. The proposed methodology is aligned with ISO 55000 family of standards approach, and therefore it can be understood as a practical asset management tool. Specific attention is paid to particular network utilities issues, characterizing assets in these companies, and the services that they provide (topology influence, reputational impact, operational losses, etc.). In addition to this, high requirements established by the Service Level Agreements (SLA), that are characteristics of network services contracts, make this method especially suitable in this application, considering in an overall way all these key aspects, providing great advantages for managing network utilities. In order to illustrate method applicability, an example extracted from a real telecommunication network use case is included.

Index Terms— Asset Management, Asset Value, Criticality, Network Utilities, Maintenance Optimization, Risk-value Assessment.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE process of “maintenance strategic management” [1] in a company coordinates and integrates all fundamental maintenance management activities in order to achieve the department objectives [2,3], aligned with the company goals.

Utilities provide services relying on network infrastructures whereby services (such as distribution of gas, water, electricity or telecommunications) are directly provided to customers in their homes, dwellings or places of business [4]. These companies are willing to assess properly the value of their assets [5, 6], considering all those aspects (obtained or expected to be obtained from the network) that provide any kind of benefit (expressed in specific terms) to the organization.

In line with the expansion process of ISO 55000 series of standards, asset’s value drivers will be not only technical aspects, but also other aspects [7] such as financial, environmental and social results, quality of service, etc.

Convergence between asset and value is a challenge in network utilities, whose infrastructure are often organized and composed of a high number and different types of assets arranged and interrelated in a hierarchical form, replicated and geographically dispersed and sometimes in non-optimal environmental conditions by distribution areas or jurisdictions [8].

In these companies, the “asset” has not to be treated in an isolated way [9,10], the variety of possible interconnections

TABLE I
NOMENCLATURE

Acronym	Definition
AHP	Analytical Hierarchy Process
AM	Asset Management
CBM	Condition-Based Maintenance
CSI	Continual Service Improvement
DNSP	Distribution Network Services Providers
FMV	Fair Market Value
ISO	International Standards Organization
IT	Information Technology
PRAz	Probabilistic Risk Assessment 1.../ categories of functional loss frequency,
RAMaf _z	Real Asset Management Average frequency of functional loss for frequency level z,
RCAff _z	Root-Cause analysis Frequency factor for frequency level z,
RCMfe _{rz}	Reliability Centered Management Boolean variable with value 1 when z is the level of the observed frequency of element r functional loss, 0 otherwise,
SLAf _r	Service Level Agreements Value for the frequency of the functional loss of element r.

among them could materialize the offered “value” by the company in a different sense, encompassing the company strategic objectives.

An asset contribution of the network must be analyzed not only focusing on network’s availability, reliability and quality of service [11], but also focusing on the losses of the expected value that can decrease revenues and increase costs [12]. In this sense, Rubio-Loyola et al. (2015) [13] discuss the need for optimization of the business value of the network infrastructure, modelling the way the performance of services offered by network operators has a direct impact on its reputation, on its revenue due to new customer subscriptions, and also on penalties that can apply when services are not provided to an acceptable quality level.

Asset criticality can help to establish priorities to manage maintenance work with limited resources [14, 15,17], and

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considering predictable and/or unpredictable circumstances that may happen due to an asset or its neighboring assets [16].

With this intention, this paper proposes a criticality assessment methodology to materialize the “value” provided by the assets of the network, considering the strengths and weaknesses due to the network topology, existing demand and environmental risk, which has a great influence on the delivered services [8]. Therefore, two are the main purposes of this research:

- To define a quantitative method to assess the value and risk of the assets, according to the existing company strategy,
- To ensure the adaptability and flexibility of this method to face changes in network configuration, assets reliability, and business aspects.

The process of network assets criticality analysis is based in the one proposed by Crespo et al. 2016 [18], now incorporating network topology analysis according to the importance of the associated risks to this factor [19]. A systematic basis for deciding what assets we can assume a certain level of risk [20] (ranked), with a certain maintenance management program [18], is provided.

The proposed method has been fully implemented in a telecommunications company. The results have been promising, improving the availability of the network by 0.73% (from 98.5% to 99.23%) and reducing 10% of the maintenance overall budget in the same period. This model has also been implemented in three oil & gas network and in two electric networks of national importance with similar results in maintenance overall budget.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents a brief summary of related work. In Section III, an introduction about the importance of the network conservation and its consequences is presented from a business point of view, as basis of the network infrastructure evaluation. Then in Section IV, the proposed criticality analysis process for network utilities is developed in a mathematical model considering different network topologies and applying it in a real case about a telecom network utility. Finally, conclusions are shown in Section 4 of the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we review some references on criticality analysis, risk and value assessment, and its application on network utilities and IT services. There are different methods in literature to assess risks and asset’s criticality, some based on qualitative techniques and others based on quantitative techniques depending on the available and trusted information and data.

Risk analyses are the “core” of a proper maintenance and dependability analysis [21]. Tangible and intangible aspects based on service experiences have to be considered and an overall lifecycle approach is recommended by asset management standards, to appreciate how short-term decision may influence long-term performance [5, 6].

The proposed methodology for asset criticality analysis is performed during the operational phase and for maintenance purposes. Therefore, it is different to criticality analysis for

asset design purposes. In the case of analysis in the design phase, the objective is more linked to asset reliability assessment, trying to identify critical areas so that different design alternatives can be optimized and compared [22]. Description of specific techniques for criticality analysis during design can be found in MIL-STD-1629A [23], also in the works of Palaez and Bowles [24] and Pillay and Wang [25]. These techniques use, for instance, the Risk Priority Number (RPN) method, fuzzy logic, or approximate reasoning to prioritize failure modes (not assets).

In reference to network utilities risk-based assessment, some authors concentrate their efforts on evaluating significant interactions (called critical incidents) that provoke positive and negative feelings of customers concerning service issues, such as those related to the ability to respond to contingencies, the reliability and the security of the service, safety and environmental preservation, etc [26]. The process approach is more common in network and IT services analysis than asset approach [27].

Current approaches to support Continual Service Improvement (CSI) suffer from many deficiencies, including lack of or weak visibility of business impacts, no modeling of uncertainty, difficulty in combining heterogeneous metrics, among others [28]. Value aspects are not specifically treated in the risk modeling of network and IT services. Different references propose models to measure the economic (recurring to cost or financial measurement) impact of SLA (Service Level Agreement) performance (examples can be found in [27,29,30]). Most of the existing studies of criticality analysis are based mainly on technical criteria and using simulation and modeling techniques. The hierarchy of the assets in these cases is not usually updated often, due to the work, the time and the cost that is required by the multitude of necessary simulations. However, in the present study, we look for an algorithm that can be executed in real time and therefore allows an update of the prioritization of assets in real time.

Saving the deficiencies found in previous models, the criticality method presented is a step forward, synthesizing several of these views and providing a versatile, powerful and easily implemented tool. In this sense, the most relevant points are:

- Asset as the main reference: no failure mode (as much of maintenance and dependability methods) nor risk process, as is usually the reference in IT services analysis. This method aims a practical analysis of the network through its individual assets.
- Risk is expressed in terms of value, not only financial or economic risk.
- A semi-quantitative method, but “quantitatively as possible”. First, in order to facilitate decision-making and continuous improvement [31] based on results linking the problems’ effects to their root causes. Second, in order to link decisions with risk-cost-benefit analysis, “*the knowledge of costs aids managers to justify investments...and assists them in monitoring the effectiveness of the effort made*” [32].

In conclusion, we propose a model guiding with quantitative formulae its application homogeneously, with the risk expressed in terms of value and updating according to configuration

network changes in real time during the operational phase, unlike of most existing models.

III. BACKGROUND

Network services management has to adapt to customers demand, sustaining the contracted service level agreements (SLA) [27,30]. Network utilities are exposed to many types of hazards and design safety margins may not be sufficient to cope with the expected and, most of all, unexpected stresses onto the systems, emerging from small perturbations that can cascade to large-scale consequences. Network services management can be improved by an asset management strategy. In this sense, value and risk assessment method for asset prioritization serves as first step of this approach. Both, “risk-based” and “business value-oriented” assessment methods can properly include evaluating network topology key aspects and additional criteria locational and hierarchical connections among network assets.

If we concentrate on utilities networks maintenance management models, the majority of the papers found in literature only cover the management function for an individual and specific type of network (water, gas, electricity and telecommunications) [33, 34, 35]. Also, these works try to cover specific aspects of network maintenance management (reliability assessment, network monitoring, network risk analysis, etc.) rather than comprehensive network management models [36, 37, 38, 39].

Criticality analysis, in terms that are proposed in this work, is a suitable and very practical tool to deal with these aims. This includes the elicitation of objective value assessment factors and the treatment of risk assessment in value terms. A risk measure particularized and located in each single network asset $Risk = Probability \times Consequences$ (classical risk model [40]), focused on *Probability* of failure of the asset and searching to provide an objective measure of failure *Consequences* in terms of value.

To effective control of network service and business sustainability, value consequences evaluation method allows consider not only cost impacts, but also operative, reputational, environmental legal, financial, etc. Table 2 adapt most frequently value criteria (taken from Gómez and Crespo (2012) [26], Zio (2016) [41], Crespo 2016) to the network use case according with expert experience. The main difficulty of this methodology is to select the proper criteria to represent consequences, the weight of them and the consistency among them and their scale values [18]. The selection of these parameters is crucial for adjustment to the company strategy and for the complexity of the criticality evaluation process. A very complex process can drive to bad results (missing information, unreliable assessments, incoherencies in asset evaluation, etc.), and even pushing the organization to desist before the end of the process.

Based on failure events, their likelihood of occurrence provides a narrow relationship between network conservation and provided value to customers by levels of aggregation, determining the level of required maintenance actions, in order to properly sustain the service level agreements over time. In the other hand, to assess the real risk and criticality in a network, we must consider vulnerability and resilience under the dynamic complexity with interactions among nodes through

link dependences with other neighbors (Network Topology). Therefore, network criticality should not only consider reliability but also the ability to recover from disruptions, minimizing the impact on health, safety, security, economics and social well-being [42]. That is, not only functional, but also topological.

IV. CRITICALITY ANALYSIS PROCESS DEVELOPMENT

From now on, it is described the process to get the criticality evaluation of the different assets in the network, defining the mathematical model that supports the process and applying it in the practical case step by step. As main point of the proposed method is the integration “risk-based” and “business value-oriented” perspectives. In Fig. 1 a series of stages are shown, which will be sequentially introduced in different sections to follow in order to properly manage criticality assessment and that may be used to support decision-making process inside each one.

The procedure to follow in order to carry out an assets criticality analysis following “risk-based” and “business value-oriented” perspectives could be then depicted as follows:

Fig. 1 Criticality Analysis Process Development

These stages have also been defined in order to facilitate the methodology implementation in a computerized management system, searching to record historical data and automation in formulae application over thousands of assets and based on several variables (quantitative or qualitative) that can be obtained and linked from other systems; and providing a practical way to re-utilize it in different companies of the same sector by dragging and dropping. In order to present the analysis process and the mathematical model implementation, a practical case for telecommunication network is introduced step by step Scope Definition & Available Data Analysis

The presented use case is focused on telecommunication network analysis, which has been extracted and adapted from a real use case. A crucial point comes from the interpretation of strategic vision of the business in the telecommunication service provider. Guaranteeing the contracted SLA is one of the key management objectives for this type of company [27], [28]. In this sense, the high level of interdependence between network assets and the actual number of network assets to be maintained is particularly relevant. In consequence, the value-risk criteria must be linked to the measurement of the service level and must be homogeneous, so that the relative importance of each asset to the service provided over the network can be elicited.

The scope of the process consists on identifying the risk level of the network through its assets, or in its assets, and providing objective prioritization criteria for mitigation plans to address them in a cost-effective and efficient manner. By doing so we ensure that maintenance actions are effective, applying resources where they really need, and at last, reducing the direct and indirect maintenance cost due to failures in the network, in this example, a telecommunications network.

On the other hand, to ensure the required level of information and knowledge about the systems and their historic behavior within the network services development, the analysis includes the following information sources:

- *Criticality Analysis team*: diverse expert role: involved in the operational context of networks (operations, maintenance, processes, safety, and environment).

TABLE 2
VALUE ASPECTS FOR SEVERITY CRITERIA COMPOSITION IN RISK AND CRITICALITY ANALYSIS

Category	Value aspects
Business-oriented	Loss of earnings (monetary assessment) of consequences. Focusing the criterion on system functionality in all the failure downtimes. Life-cycle-cost, including the estimation of all the corrective costs per failure. Market drivers as bad reputation due to failures, provoking loss of customers and/or company image. Market segmentation of customers in classes, by reporting income to the company, corporate image or strategic / social importance.
Operation and Maintenance	Communication, control, human and organizational factors, logistics, etc. Accessibility to repair the asset in its own site.
Service quality and Performance	Unavailability as accumulated service downtimes. Unreliability centred on the probability of functional failure occurrence. Capacity usage from designed maximum or nominal capacity as the basis of service aggregation from customers to the core of the network or generation nodes.
Industrial Security	Evaluating possible impacts of cascading service outages. Evaluating possible effects in surrounding assets or infrastructures.
Legal environmental and H&S	Monetary H&S / Environmental consequences. According to the principle of European new environmental legislation, those who harm the environment, will pay to clean it. These issues also affect customers and society's perception of the company, loss of customers and/or company image.
Geographical service coverage	Technical coverage of the asset and, Number of customers supported by it.
Location parameters	Reachability easily not far away from the maintenance office, due to long distances among network components. Geographical or Environmental influence in the asset risk, such us earthquakes, mudslides, steep vegetation.
Connectivity parameters	Betweenness of nodes oriented to centrality importance of in the network and path diversity.

- *Engineering data*: technical characteristic about assets and the systems where they are integrated, including data for functional loss effect evaluation.
- *Operational data*: including current failures frequency and functional loss effect regarding operation and capacity impacts.

- *Customer Relationship data*: about all the interactions with the customers, segmented and orientated from a marketing point of view.
- *Financial and Controlling data*: centered on a cost point of view, with the aim of obtaining tangible cost and modelling intangible costs from a business point of view.

1. Infrastructure Model Selection

In this step, the real infrastructure can be model in more or less hierarchical levels. This stage is concerned about determination of logical network architecture, deciding the number of hierarchical levels and the relationship among them. In some cases in oil&gas sector, we have found up to seven hierarchical levels, the more hierarchical level there are, the more assets detail we have to manage and record in our system to automate the criticality values on real-time. As well as a same type of asset can be found in different levels of hierarchy, so its inclusion has to be systematic and procedural-based process covering from the initial stage or scope. The methodology analysis can be done separately in each of these levels or in a general way considering all the assets and levels. Thanks to manage this stage individually, the idea is to provide in a system, historic library of application of the methodology in several projects or companies with the aim to facilitate the data analysis sampling different scenarios. In this case, the levels description is related to the phases of processing of the telecommunication service. The selected infrastructure model in this example is organized and interrelated in four main parts: generation, where the services are generated; transmission, where the services are transformed and transported to remote areas by connections with huge capacity; distribution, technical sites to disperse the services within each area; and customer links, to supply the services to the customers.

2. Infrastructure definition

In stage 3, physical architecture is defined, considering the hierarchical levels involved in the study and the real connections among assets in the same level and if there are with upper and lower assets from other hierarchical levels. The idea of distinguishing between steps 2 and 3 is to facilitate the re-utilization of the infrastructure models in different criticality assessment projects or companies. The defined logical network architecture in stage 2 can be assigned to another list of assets reorganizing the hierarchical structure, or the same list of assets can be reorganized according to other logical network architecture testing different scenarios. This has been very useful to apply the methodology among different companies in the same sector (oil&gas) and within an international company in different countries.

The criticality process can use the same severity levels for all the different levels of the infrastructure model or define different ones in each level.

Fig. 2 Practical case Telecommunications Network Topology and Betweenness coefficients

Practical use case focuses on the second level of a telecommunication network described above: the transmission level. In order to make an easy understanding of the proposed method, a simplified case is presented. It includes eight nodes connected among them and the assets (routers) included within these nodes that provide the service functionalities at this transmission level. Network (A-H) schema of use case is depicted in Fig. 2.

3. Severity-Value Factors and Scale Definition

On the basis of the most frequently evaluated criteria, summarized above in Table 2, a specific and deeper analysis has been done adjusting these to the telecommunication network use case. To do this, a number of work meetings were programming with the participation of expert roles. These roles are diverse and complementary, according to the different aspects related to the accurate characterization of the functional context of the studied network (management, customer service, operation, maintenance, processes, safety, and environment). As a result of the meetings, pre-selected most relevant factors to compose the assessment of different criteria are presented hereafter.

1) Severity-Value Factors Definition

The number of selected severity criteria has to be reduced as much as possible, not making complicated model implementation and the interpretation of the results. But, other hand, criteria have to be enough to describe accurately the reality of the network and avoiding dependence among factors. Authors recommend, from our experience, to aggregate all the factors using four to six criteria. From the analysis above, the determination of the final severity criteria to include have been realized in four criteria to compose the model for this case: Loss Exposure Criterion (LE), Environmental and Safety Criterion (ES), Network Security Criterion (NS) and Social Importance Criterion (SI).

Searching quantification on mathematical formulas, allowing correct interpretation of the importance of each criterion, specific meetings with experts had been done. In this case, services are in a QoS-based pricing scheme and the customers are organized in pricing classes based on the type of their requested services and their corresponding QoS prerequisites [57]. We have considered two service classes consisting of residential customers and, social sites or large enterprises customers. Moreover, the adopted pricing scheme for residential customers in this case is Flat-rate Pricing (to charge a one-off fee for every user, regardless the usage of the user), and for social sites and large enterprises is Usage-based Pricing

TABLE 3
TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS EMPLOYED IN THE METHOD AND MODEL

Term/ Abbre.	Definition
o	1... k element or asset analysed,
i	1... n criteria to measure severity of an element functional loss.
j	1... m levels of possible effects of a functional loss for any criteria,
M_i	Maximum level of admissible effect for criteria i , with $M_i \leq m$, $\forall i$,
MS	Maximum severity value.
S_{ij}	Severity of the effect j for the severity criteria i ,
pe_{oij}	Potential effect j of criteria i for the functional loss of element o ,
S_o	Severity of the functional loss of element o ,
w_i	Weight given to the severity criteria i by experts, with $\sum_{i=1}^n w_i = 1$,
e_{ij}	Effect j of the severity criteria i ,
v_{ij}	Fractional value of effect j for the severity criteria i ,
z	1... l categories of functional loss frequency,
af_z	Average frequency of functional loss for frequency level z ,
ff_z	Frequency factor for frequency level z ,
$f_{e_{oz}}$	Boolean variable with value 1 when z is the level of the observed frequency of element o functional loss, 0 otherwise,
f_o	Value for the frequency of the functional loss of element o ,
f_o^y	It is f_o including proportionality,
C_o	$S_o \cdot f_o$: Criticality of element o ,
f'_o	New probability of the effect j of criteria i for the failure of o ,
S'_o	New observed severity of the functional loss of element o ,
C'_o	New criticality of element o ,
$CNPV$	Customer Net Present Value,
\overline{cc}_o	All costs in materials, human resources and supplies to solve the failure in the asset o ,
n_{co}	Concerned customers per failure of element o ,
CC_o	Corrective costs of node o ,
UC_o	Loss of earnings by service unavailability in node o ,
LE_o	Loss of earnings of node o ,
BP_o	Bad propaganda effects over current customers in node o ,
BR_o	Bad reputation effects over potential customers in node o ,
RF_o	Recover Fair Market Value,
NS_o	Network Security Criterion Cost of element o ,
T	Mean life time cycle of CNPV,
n_{mo}	Average market coverage ratio of customers in the area of element o ,
\overline{cp}_o	Mean cost in publicity to compensate the bad reputation,
\overline{tr}_o	Average reestablishment time of the element o , and T_r is defined reestablishment time per contract,
\bar{t}	Average reestablishment time in all the elements of the network,
$P_{abo}(t_{ro})$	Abandon probability per customer related to the offered reestablishment time by the contract,
$\rho(t)$	Boolean variable indicates with $\rho=1$ that $\overline{tr}_o > T_r$, and with $\rho=0$ otherwise,
LE_o	Loss Exposure Criterion Cost of element o ,
l_{ESo}	H&S / Environmental consequences level of the element o ,
l_{RFo}	Recover FMV consequences level of the element o ,
P_{aco}	Probability of occurrence of an H&S / Environmental accident due to a failure of element o ,
ES_o	Environmental and Safety Criterion Cost of element o ,
SI_o	Social Importance Criterion Cost of element o ,
$b(o)$	Betweenness coefficient of the element o ,
\hat{B}	Maximum betweenness in the network,
$d(k, s)$	Number of shortest paths that pass through the element o ,
$d_{k,s}$	Number of all the shortest paths that connect elements k and s ,
x_o	Remaining capacity in terms of customers of element o ,
n_f	Number of failures with service interruption in the network,
γ_{xy}	Proportionality Factor due to extra degradation by locational conditions in the zone of element o .

(to charge according to the amount and pattern of usage of each individual user) [58]. In order to simplify, we have used the Customer Net Present Value as a mean over all the residential customer, and we have included the contribution of social sites

or large enterprises adding a new factor.

Below in this section, the quantification method applied in four criteria will be introduced. Terms and abbreviations employed to this end are included in Table 3.

a) *Loss Exposure Criterion (LE)*

This criterion has to concrete the number of economic losses due to functional breakage [13], not only the direct losses by corrective costs, but also resulting in lost earnings due to service interruption time. Equations (1) and (2) represent the consequences caused by a failure in the network with respect to the criterion of Loss Exposure and are measured as a part of the Customer Net Present Value for the company (CNPV). CNPV can be formalized including total income from a customer during a period of time minus all the costs required to serve that customer, such as selling costs, acquisition costs, retention costs and advertising costs [43]. This concept is key to translate consequences in terms of customer and business impacts.

Direct costs:

- Corrective costs (CC_o) in a node-o: They include all costs in materials, human resources and supplies to solve the failure in the asset. They are measured as a percentage of the CNPV as a reference. Then for an asset (node-o, router), these costs are concretized as a ratio between the mean corrective cost (\overline{cc}_o) per failure in the asset per each concerned customer (n_{co} in total), and the CNPV. This cost depends mainly on the maintainability characteristics of the asset, the higher involved resources and supplies, most of all due to complex and with high capacity assets, the higher corrective costs are.

$$CC_o = CNPV \cdot n_{co} \cdot \frac{\overline{cc}_o}{CNPV} \quad (1)$$

- Loss of earnings by service unavailability (UC_o): It corresponds to the amount of money that the provider stops earning because of an interruption in the service it provides. Due to the operational reliability of the network, the potential impact of a functional loss of an asset is reflected by the service interruption, being proportional to time, to the unavailability of the service per failure related to the service re-establishment time (\overline{tr}_o) against the total time (T) of customer life-cycle, and so determining the discounting Customer Net Present Value (CNPV) per each concerned customer (n_{co} in total) and failure. In view of equation (2), the greater the number of affected customers, the re-establishment time (\overline{tr}_o) or the CNPV, the grater the consequences due to the Loss of Earnings. This cost depends again on the asset maintainability.

$$UC_o = CNPV \cdot n_{co} \cdot \frac{\overline{tr}_o}{T} \quad (2)$$

Consequently, for each asset, (see Equation 3) the Loss Exposure costs are the sum of the corrective cost and loss of earnings over the CNPV per the impacted customers over the re-establishment time (\overline{tr}_o).

$$LE_o = CC_o + UC_o = CNPV \cdot n_{co} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{\overline{cc}_o}{CNPV} + \frac{\overline{tr}_o}{T} \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

b) *Environmental and Safety Criterion (ES)*

Based on Legal parameters, H&S / Environmental consequences of an asset (node-o) can be produced by failures, and they can harm the environment or people. To evaluate this perspective, we have employed the Wireman (1998) [44] method, which has been widely used to evaluate these risks, reducing the consequences categories in the following levels l_{ESo} (based on MIL-STD-882C standard [45]): Catastrophe; numerous fatalities; damage or penalty over \$500,000. Critical fatality, damage or penalty \$100,000 to \$500,000. Extremely serious injury (amputation, permanent disability); damage or penalty \$10,000 to \$100,000. Minor cuts, bruises, bumps; minor damage or penalty 1,000 to \$10,000.

Although in a failure event, the risk about H&S / Environmental or penalty could appear or not, that is, there is a probability that the accident occurs once the failure has occurred (P_{aco}). Therefore, the reduced and modified levels of probability for this risk are four: Quite possible (has an even 50% chance) with a $P_{aco} = 0.5$. Remotely possible with a $P_{aco} = 0.1$. Conceivable (has never happened after many years of exposure) with a $P_{aco} = 0.05$. Practically impossible (has never happened) with a $P_{aco} = 0.01$.

$$ES_o = l_{ESo} \cdot P_{aco} \quad (4)$$

c) *Social Importance Criterion (SI)*

As it is said before, the social perspective is crucial in network utilities. In this line, failures decrease customer satisfaction, transmitting bad propaganda into the market (up to 10 partners [46]), modifying customer perception of service quality (up to 44% of customer losses [47]). Then for an asset (node-o), bad propaganda due to failures could have effects on current customers or potential customer. In addition, over critical and strategic customers are usually more exigent in-service performance and quality, and we should consider the indirect costs due to their dissatisfaction. Consequently, this criterion is related to the consequences of transmitted bad reputation, by normal and critical customers. Besides, the supplied services become but even more critical in emergencies due to important accidents or disasters that can impact heavily in society. Consequently, the importance of customers opinion does not have to be evaluated only with an increment of CNPV, but to be assessed taking into count the overall impacts of a bad supply of services to them, that could detonate high bad reputation in the society. Impacts go beyond the repair costs and penalties, because it has to consider the impact on earnings and market value, and so if the continuity of supplied services is crucial facing catastrophes.

- Bad propaganda effects over current customers (BP_o). It represents the loss of earnings that the company would suffer due to the abandonment of dissatisfied customers for the service provided. In this case, current customers (that have suffering failures) could decide to abandon the service with a certain probability $P_{abo}(tr_o)$ related to the service re-establishment time (\overline{tr}_o) against the offered by

the contract or existing standard market service level agreements (T_r). The probability to abandon has been studied in real market scenario in the critical assets in this telecom company due to its influence in customer claims and churn rates in reference [48]. This study will rely on a Weibull distribution and Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) to obtain the Weibull equation that reflects the probability to abandon per current customer and per each failure based on the mean service re-establishment time, and where it is shown a direct relation among maintainability and customer dissatisfaction, producing significant financial consequences. Weibull density function is some of the most broadly used probability density functions in reliability, being the former for allowing easier calculations while the latter for allowing the representation of other probability functions such as exponential, Rayleigh or normal probability functions as well. In this sense, it could describe the most frequent curves for the failure rate directly, or by modifications, or by a combination of several Weibull curves ones [49]. In this case, the study supports the quantitative estimation of this probability, simplifying by a 2-parameters Weibull equation.

$$BP_o = CNPV \cdot n_{co} \cdot P_{abo} \left(\frac{\bar{t}_{ro}}{T_r} \right) \quad (5)$$

- Bad reputation effects over potential customers (BR_o). It represents the loss of earnings due to potential customers who have not finally contracted services due to the bad propaganda of dissatisfied customers. Market reputation is crucial to acquire new customers. The transmitted bad propaganda outside the company to potential customers, could decrease their intention to contract the services. The cost estimation of acquiring a new customer influenced by bad propaganda is twice than a non-negative-influenced customer [46,47]. The influenced potential customers are estimated through the market coverage ratio of customers (n_{mo}) in the area of technical influence of the asset. Once, CNPV is used as reference to concretize the cost of capturing new influenced customers through a proportional ratio with the mean cost in publicity (\bar{cp}_o) inside the CNPV to compensate the bad reputation and depending on the service re-establishment time the relation (\bar{t}_{ro}) with the offered by the contract (T_r). But only when (\bar{t}_{ro}) > (T_r), which is indicated by the Boolean variable $\rho=1$ and $\rho=0$ otherwise.

$$BR_o = CNPV \cdot n_{co} \cdot (1 - n_{mo}) \cdot \frac{\bar{cp}_o}{CNPV} \cdot \rho \quad (6)$$

Recover FMV (RF_o). The associated consequences costs to this criterion, have been related to the amount of earnings in risk plus the necessary publicity to recover the Fair Market Value (FMV) due to bad reputation and the losses in the capital stock during a year (up to 15% consistent with [50]). Although the network utilities companies have to compensate the bad propaganda by publicity in affected areas by asset failures, they also have to consider the economic impact when social sites or large

enterprises are supplied by the asset, because it provides services that are key to support the performance of the own social service: such as public administrations, hospitals, fire station, transport stations, airports, military buildings, ports, etc. Subsequently, this effect is considered an amplification factor of the criticality. Accordingly, failures an asset (node-o) can harm the FMV, and to evaluate this we have employed the same levels categories of ES criterion (l_{ESo}) with a remote probability $P_{aco} = 50\%$ of chance, obtaining (l_{RFo}): More than three social sites or large enterprises, failure impact estimated over \$250,000. Social Sites: such as public administrations, hospitals, fire station, transport stations, airports, military buildings, ports, etc. Less than three social sites or large enterprises with failure impact between \$50,000 to \$250,000. More than 10 Medium and Small enterprises with failure impact between \$5,000 to \$50,000. Less than 10 Medium and Small enterprises or regular customers with failure impact less than \$5,000.

$$RF_o = l_{RFo} \quad (7)$$

Consequently, for each asset, (see Equation 8) the Social Importance criterion (SI_o). is the sum of the bad propaganda effects over current customers (BP_o), bad reputation effects over potential customers (BR_o), and the Recover FMV (RF_o) corrective cost and loss of earnings over the CNPV per the impacted customers, and the indirect costs due to the exposed customers in risk to abandon the service over the re-establishment time (\bar{t}_{ro}), and the associated indirect costs of influenced partners.

$$SI_o = BP_o + BR_o + RF_o = \left[CNPV \cdot n_{co} \cdot \left(P_{abo} \left(\frac{\bar{t}_{ro}}{T_r} \right) + (1 - n_{mo}) \cdot \frac{\bar{cp}_o}{CNPV} \cdot \rho \right) \right] + l_{RFo} \quad (8)$$

d) Network Security Criterion (NS)

This criterion summarizes the possible impacts of cascading service outages and the possible effects on surrounding assets or infrastructures. For this purpose, this criterion correlates them with parameters about network topology, since that networks are dynamic and suffer several configuration and operational changes. Network topology is the logical representation of the network as a combination of nodes linked by edges (distances among nodes), and in line with the purpose of showing the dynamic importance of a node to transport the services from a vulnerability point of view [51,52], there is a graph coefficient that can be derived for an asset (node-o).

Betweenness coefficient of a node is a measure of the fraction of shortest paths between any two nodes going through the vertex and is one of the widely used shortest path-based centrality metrics for the complex network analysis [53]. Betweenness centrality describes if a node has a high number of shortest paths from the rest nodes on the graph. This coefficient is based on communication flow and with this parameter, we search how a node is able to assist to others or to be assisted by the neighbors to deliver services in case of failures and, evaluating cascade failures, and also how its neighbors can survive receiving services from it. It is a good

measure of the centrality in a network and the capability to route services from other nodes in emergency cases.

We have compounded the network security criterion based on betweenness centrality graph coefficient in a normalized way, using the maximum betweenness number of graph nodes (\hat{B}). This coefficient evaluates the shortest paths that pass through the node- o from all the total number of shortest paths between every other pair of nodes, (see Equation 9) where $d(k, s)$ is the number of shortest paths that pass through node- o and $d_{k,s}$ is all the shortest paths that connect k and s nodes.

$$b(o) = \left[\sum_{k \neq o \neq s} \frac{d(k, s)}{d_{k,s}} \right] / \hat{B} \quad (9)$$

In order to show the properties of this coefficient, the following Fig. 3 presents the values of betweenness coefficients in typical network topologies (star, ring, in a series) derived from Fig. 2, Fig. 3-a, 3-b and 3-c respectively; as a token of centrality importance of the node. Where in the centrality value is well represented in the node F in Fig. 3-a, equals centrality value in a ring topology for all the nodes in Fig. 3-b, and maximum centrality value in nodes B and D in Fig. 3-c.

Fig. 3 Betweenness coefficients examples.

From a survival point of view, the betweenness coefficient ranks the nodes according to their influence in the neighbors, higher values (near to 1) indicate multiple redundant paths to be reconfigured to support their neighbors in case of node failures, see in Fig. 2. The topological importance of the nodes in a survivability point of view can be shown by betweenness coefficients, and for this objective, the cost of consequences due to bad redundant paths configuration is considered an opportunity cost because these could be utilized in emergency cases to support failures of their neighbors. Therefore, the remaining node capacity (x_o) in terms of possible customers (CNPV) could support other nodes in the mean re-establishment time \bar{t}_{ro} against the total time (T) of customer life-cycle for all the failures with service interruption (n_f) in the network. In a failure event, the support of other node could appear or not, that is, there is a probability that the support occurs once the failure has occurred in the node, so betweenness coefficient is as a probability for the occurrence of this support due to redundancy by paths.

$$NS_o = CNPV \cdot b(o) \cdot x_o \cdot n_f \cdot \frac{\bar{t}_{ro}}{T} \quad (10)$$

2) Scale Definition of Severity Factors

In a second step, the levels inside each criterion have to be established in the used scale in this model, from 0 to 100. Although, firstly, it is necessary to define the “non-admissible” effects for some criteria which represent those consequences, referred to a specifically defined criterion that is considered unacceptable by the organization. Therefore, this level of

impact can be identified as that saturate severity assessment, thus those assets where “non-admissible” effects can appear will have the maximum severity 100 (the top level of this criterion). Besides, in any criterion, we could consider as the lower level “No Affection (N/A)” effect if it is needed.

With these considerations, description of levels of the four severity criteria are included below:

- Loss Exposure Criterion (LE_o): Based on Pareto analysis as in frequency levels, we have developed 4 costs categories depending on the cost distribution and finding averages costs and the corresponding factors for each effect classification level: Very High (10%), High (20%), Medium (20%) and Low (50%).
- Environmental and Safety Criterion (ES_o): Based on William T. Fine (1971) factors, where the risk score is defined in three levels: Immediate (correction required; activity should be discontinued until hazard is reduced), Urgent (requires attention as soon as possible), and Possible or acceptable (hazard should be eliminated without delay, but the situation is not an emergency). As a result, we have developed the following levels: Non-admissible with $ES_o = l_{ESo} \cdot P_{aco}$ equals or higher than \$250,000. Urgent with ES_o between \$50,000 and \$250,000. Possible with ES_o between \$5,000 and \$50,000. N/A with ES_o equals or minor than \$5,000.
- Social Importance Criterion (SI_o): Accordingly, our four types of customers, the classification level in this effect criterion are the following: More than three social sites or large enterprises, failure impact estimated over \$250,000, valuing the impact as “non-admissible”. High impact with less than three social sites or large enterprises with failure impact between \$50,000 to \$250,000. Medium impact with more than 10 Medium and Small enterprises with failure impact between \$5,000 to \$50,000. Low impact with less than 10 Medium and Small enterprises or regular customers with failure impact less than \$5,000.
- Network Security Criterion (NS_o): By virtue of translating the impact to a term of cost, and once the Pareto analysis has been utilized searching the distribution on 4 costs categories with their averages costs following the corresponding developed levels for the Loss Exposure Criterion (LE). Very High (10%), High (20%), Medium (20%) and Low (50%).

Thus, consistency in the Severity calculation of one element with respect to another is ensured, but also remarking a nonadmissible situation such as the determined by Marketing and H&S departments in SI and ES respectively, searching consensus among conflicting worries about the business value or costs. In our model, we have used 100 as the maximum value for overall severity of the network assets. The relative values for the different effects for each criterion are presented in a matrix (see Table 4), where units for these relative values are based on cost.

TABLE 4
EFFECTS MATRIX PER FUNCTIONAL LOSS

Criteria to measure Severity			
LE	ES	NS	SI
Category of effects per criteria and functional loss			
50,000	Non admissible	50,000	Non admissible
20,000	50,000	20,000	50,000

5,000	5,000	5,000	5,000
0	0	0	0

4. *Weighting Severity Factors*

At this point, it is addressed the definition of the criteria weights and levels. Four levels of severity have been used for the evaluation of each of the four established criteria. In our case, in order to assign criteria weights that represent their relative importance within the model, it is recommended to employ a formalized method as AHP (Analytical Hierarchy Process) to obtain the subjective judgments about criteria importance from the experts involved in the meetings. In AHP, thanks to hierarchical structuring of decision-making, pairwise comparisons, redundant judgments and the eigenvector method for deriving weights and consistency considerations, the criteria weights combine both objective measures and subjective preferences, quantifying relative priorities for a given set of alternatives on a ratio scale [54,55]. The recommendation is to employ this method in few numbers of criteria, because the major drawback in the use of AHP is the effort required to make all pair-wise comparisons. In the example of this paper, w_i , weight given to the severity criteria i by experts, resulting from the AHP analysis are assumed to be equal to:

$$[w_i] = 25, 20, 25, 30, \text{ where } [i] = LE, ES, NS, SI \quad (11)$$

In the mathematical model proposed, the effects severity matrix has been pre-defined previously, for any element included in the analysis (r), as follows:

$$S_{ij} = \begin{cases} MS, & \text{for } M_i < j \leq m, \quad \forall i \\ w_i v_{ij}, & \text{for } 1 \leq j \leq M_i, \quad \forall i \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Where

MS : Maximum value for overall severity.

M_i : Maximum level of admissible effect for criteria i , with $M_i \leq m, \forall i$ where $[i]=LE, ES, NS, SI$ criterion and $[M_i]=4,3,4,3$ as maximum levels of admissible effects for each criteria.

$v_{ij} = \frac{e_{ij}}{e_{ik}}$, with $k = M_i$ and $j \leq M_i$, and with $v_{ij} = 1$ for $j = M_i$ and $\forall i$, with e_{ij} as the effect j of the severity criteria i , and v_{ij} is the fractional value of effect j for the severity criteria i .

Thus, the corresponding effects severity matrix (according to Equation 12, and for $MS=100$) is included in Table 5. Notice how a non-admissible effect of SI will count for 100 (maximum value) regardless of the effect in any other criteria. Let's see the interpretation of Tables 4 and 5 as an example:

- If its functional loss happens, node A, with effects on LE criterion with potential cost of 3,238.92 \$, on ES criterion with potential impact of 5,000 \$, on NS criterion with potential cost of 20,181 \$, and on SI criterion with less than three social sites or large enterprises (SLE); so, the severity effect levels respectively are 1 in LE, 2 in ES, 3 in NS and 3 in SI.
- The correspondent points of severity effects are 0 in LE, 10 in ES, 10 in NS and 30 in SI, then the total severity criteria are 50.

TABLE 5
EFFECTS SEVERITY PER FUNCTIONAL LOSS, S_{ij}

Criteria to measure Severity			
LE ($w_1=25\%$)	ES ($w_2=20\%$)	NS ($w_3=25\%$)	SI ($w_4=30\%$)
Category of effects per criteria and functional loss			
25	Non admissible: 100	25	Non admissible: 100
10	20	10	30
5	5	5	5
0	0	0	0

5. *Frequency Factor and Scale Definition*

Based on the unreliability, centered on the probability of functional failure occurrence, the frequency levels are determined, and using Pareto analysis (percentage of elements inside each level by the meetings of experts) according to 4 ($z=1..l$) frequency categories depending on the functional loss frequency: very high (10%), high (25%), medium (25%) and low functional loss frequency (40%), see Table 6. In this failure probability, several failures modes (electrical, wired and configuration failures) are considered for a node. The main parameters that influence the failure probability are the operation time, the ratio between used capacity versus maximum capacity, and temperature and humidity as locational factors. In the mathematical model, af_z is the average frequency of functional loss for frequency level z , and the frequency factor vector is ff_z .

TABLE 6
CALCULATION OF FREQUENCY FACTORS PER SELECTED FUNCTIONAL LEVELS

Asset	f/y	Asset	f/y	Category (z)	% (z)	af_z	ff_z
A	7	G	8	Very high	10%	8	8
B	1	A	7	High	25%	6.5	6.5
C	4	H	6				
D	3	C	4	Medium	25%	3.5	3.5
E	1	D	3				
F	1	E	1	Low	40%	1	1
G	8	B	1				
H	6	F	1				

The mathematical representation of the frequency of functional losses for an asset (o) is expressed in a vector fe_{oz} of (z) Boolean variables according to the levels of functional loss frequency:

$$fe_{oz} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{when } z \text{ is the observed frequency} \\ & \text{category } ffz \text{ of element } r \text{ functional loss} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The frequency factor to apply to one element would be the result of the following scalar product:

$$f_o = \sum_{z=1}^{z=l} ff_z \cdot fe_{oz} \quad (14)$$

In our example for the asset A , the functional loss frequency vector is $[fe_{Az}]=0,0,1,0$, and the frequency factor to consider finally in order to calculate its criticality is $f_A=1x0+3.5x0+6.5x1+8x0=6.5$.

6. Consistency Analysis and Criticality Levels.

In order to capture data concerning maximum potential effects, a matrix of $n \times m$ Boolean elements (pe_{oij}) are used for each asset (o), where $i: 1 \dots n$ are different severity criterion and $j: 1 \dots m$ are levels of possible effects of a functional loss for any criterion. See the resultant matrix for A asset.

$$pe_{oij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{when } j \text{ is the level of maximum potential effect of the functional loss of an element } o \text{ and for the severity criterion } i \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

$$pe_{Aij} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

Therefore, the total Severity of the functional loss of element (o) is as follows:

$$S_o = Min \left(MS, \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m pe_{oij} \cdot S_{ij} \right) \quad (17)$$

And therefore, the severity of the asset A would result in:

$$S_A = Min(100, 5 + 5 + 0 + 30) = 40 \quad (18)$$

Finally, according to the retrieved frequency factor (vector) and the severity factor (matrix) for a functional loss of an asset, concreted potential criticality is calculated as (see an example for A asset):

$$C_o = f_o \cdot S_o \quad (19)$$

$$C_A = 6.5 \cdot 40 = 260 \quad (20)$$

As a result, we could generate automatically the criticality asset ranking per hierarchical level of the network, classifying them quantitatively in three criticality categories: low, mid, or high criticality, see Table 7. Then, these categories reflect the prioritization for activity assignation from a strategic and cost point of view (business point of view). For this purpose, the amount of assets classified in each category has to be decided according to the budget segmentation of the department, in our example 15% for critical, 35% for semicritical and 50% for not critical.

TABLE 7
CRITICALITY CATEGORIES FOR ACTIVITIES PRIORITIZATION

Criticality level	% of assets	Criticality value interval	Area colour in Fig. 6 & Table 8
Critical	10	400–800	Dark grey
Semicritical	35	175-400	Grey
Not critical	55	0–175	White

Once frequency and severity factors have been defined, they have to be reviewed, avoiding:

- Their levels cannot overlap;
- There are possible values that do not fit into some of the levels;

- There are levels of these factors empty of assets;
- The sum of the weighting of the different levels are consistent with the data;
- The sum of the weighting of the different factors adds up to 100;
- There are possible technical locations of an asset without frequency and severity factors defined;
- There are assets of the same family at different levels without consistency;
- The criticality thresholds are correctly defined and congruent.

In order to control these issues to test automatically them, the developed criticality methodology has been implemented in the computerized management system, and so several warning icons are included in the software indicating each one, Fig. 6.

Fig. 4 Consistency Analysis in the software.

Besides, some graphs are incorporated in the consistency analysis. Ones showing the number and percentage of assets that have already defined a level of frequency and severity factors. Another graph indicating the number and percentage of all asset with assigned criticality and. Another group of graphs illustrating the percentage of assets in each level of frequency and severity factors; Another graph showing also the number and percentage assets in each one of the criticality levels and;

Advanced graphs and tables support the analysis with statistical information as a summary including density distribution functions and their parameters (including normal, exponential, Weibull, gamma, Poisson, and binomial) that best fit to distributions of assets in severity, frequency and criticality levels.

7. Criticality Procurement.

After the consistency analysis, it could re-adjust the levels and weights, the criticality matrix is realized, although the analysis methodology encompasses two additional studies of sustainable evolution of criticality: comparison of assets in the same or similar families/types/zones, and comparison of the asset over time.

Family/Type/Zone Asset Comparison: Assessing the criticality occurrences by families/types/zones of assets, distinguishing extreme values in severity and frequency factors. I.e., in network utilities, some special geographical or environmental circumstances could increment the normal asset degradation (such us mudslides, steep vegetation, etc.), and from risk assessment point of view, the influence of this zone

factor may obey, searching simplifying for a practical application, proportional contributions to the risk and without time dependency. Then, we would employ a component of proportionality with the failure frequency, modifying the frequency factor of an asset, from other of the similar family, with a proportional factor of probability γ_{xy} , being the multiplier factor in y number of times failure frequency of functional loss. With this proportional factor in frequency, we could model dynamic adaptation to real conditions, such as mudslides or steep vegetation. In case of proportional contribution, the frequency value of element r has to be obtained, multiplying by the proportionality factor γ_{xy} the frequency of the nodes in the same family with normal degradation. Then, the obtained frequency by proportionality will be set in the respective frequency category and obtain the final f_r^y value for the frequency of the functional loss of element r . In case of proportionality factor γ_{x2} for node A, the frequency vector will be $[f_{e_{Az}}^2]=0,0,0,1$ and the new correspondent frequency factor $f_A^2=1x0+3.5x0+6.5x0+8x1=8$.

Dynamic Comparison: Orientated to sustainable evolution with the time, it is important to compare potential criticality versus new criticality for each asset. We have previously calculated the first, and in order to so, now we have to calculate the last one, retrieved from new data for observed functional loss effects. Then, we can model the new Severity and Frequency Factors of the element (o) as follows with new effects, and the retrieved new criticality is formulated as C'_o (see example in node A with a change in frequency of failure to 4 and so the correspondent level is 2 with a value of 3,5). Due to frequency change of asset A, its criticality has been modified as semicritical instead of critical, showing this criticality reduction and improvement in the risk.

$$C'_o = f'_o \cdot S'_o \rightarrow C_{A'} = 3.5 \cdot 40 = 140 \tag{19}$$

The details for severity and criticality calculation of each node are described hereafter, in our case about a telecom company with the following average values for all the elements:

- CNPV=1,415€ with T=2 years or 17,520 hours of lifetime cycle,
- n_{co} =50 concerned customers per failure of the 2,000 total

possible customers of capacity per node,

- The corrective cost per failure is 5,640 €, then $\frac{cc_o}{CNPV} = 8\%$,
- $T_r=12h$ and for all of them $t_{ro} > T_r$ then $\rho=1$,
- $n_{mo}=25\%$ market coverage ratio of customers in the area,
- The publicity cost per influenced potential customer $\overline{cp}_o=20$ €, then $\frac{cc_o}{CNPV} = 1.41\%$,
- $P_{abo}(t)$ obtained by Weibull analysis with parameters $\beta=1.67$, $\alpha=96$ as abandon probability per customer related to the offered reestablishment time by the contract,
- $x_o=250$ customers in terms of average remaining capacity of the element for all nodes.

Based on collected data from company call center and monitoring asset systems it is determined the failure probability and the impact on the customer churn rates. Loyalty of customers depends on service reliability and, after any detected failure (proactive by monitoring) or any received claim (reactive by call centre management) due to a failure, an opinion poll is executed by call center, collecting the received and perceives customer satisfaction and correlating them with the customers abandon.

In Table 8, the reader can find the calculus in which are based each severity criterion and its correspondent severity level. The sum of all is multiplied by the frequency level to obtain the criticality per element.

The criticality analysis of the example is summarized in Fig. 4, where criticality categories are shown in boxes of grey colors. Besides, after two years the criticality analysis has been reviewed, changing for some nodes past criticality to new criticality values, that is, as a result of any improvement on reliability terms of the asset, the frequency over time was reduced, and in the opposite way, overstepped operating conditions increased the frequency over time.

In order to facilitate analyzing the difference between past and new criticality as a sample of the asset management performance, both calculations could be represented in a matrix, see in Fig. 5, past and new criticality for all the assets. Thanks to the results representation, we can audit current maintenance management, showing how good the applied

TABLE 8
CRITICALITY AND SEVERITY DETAILS PER ASSET

Node Element	Fre-quency	Criteria to measure Severity														Critica- lity
		Loss Exposure (weight: 25%)			Legal Importance (weight: 20%)				Network Security (weight: 25%)			Strategic Importance (weight: 30%)			Severity	
		FE	t_{ro}	Total €	PE1	l_{eso}	Paco	Total €	PE2	b	Total €	PE3	l_{RFo}	Total €	PE4	
A	6.5	12	5.688,46	5	100,000	0.05	5,000	5	0.35	2,629	0	<3SLE	52.162	30	40	260
B	1	12	5.688,46	5	100,000	0.50	50,000	20	0.44	3,305	0	>10SME	7.162	5	30	30
C	3.5	15	5.700,57	5	150,000	0.50	75,000	20	0.00	0	0	<3SLE	70.616	30	55	192,5
D	3.5	12	5.688,46	5	5,000	0.01	50	0	0.13	976	0	>10SME	7.162	5	10	35
E	1	16	5.704,61	5	5,000	0.50	2,500	0	0.97	9,714	5	<3SLE	70.962	30	40	40
F	1	18	5.712,69	5	50,000	0.05	2,500	0	1.00	11,267	5	>3SLE	271.692	100	100	100
G	8	13	5.692,50	5	5,000	0.01	50	0	0.06	488	0	>10SME	24.966	5	10	80
H	6.5	14	5.696,54	5	250,000	0.10	25,000	5	0.22	1,927	0	>3SLE	270.284	100	100	650

activities are for an asset, either reduce the frequency or the consequences. A asset is an example of the first case, and H asset is for the last case. In addition, if node C has changed its locational environment, an example with more radiation can increase temperature, a proportional factor x3 has been obtained to model this circumstance, and so C³ is introduced in the matrix. The probability of abandon has been evaluated with data of two years, in the beginning of the study, but our recommendation is to re-calculate all the criticality process every two years in order to observe the improvements in frequencies and consequences due to implemented actions plans.

ff_z	8		G				C ³				
	6.5					A			H'		H
	3.5		D			A'	C				
	1				B	E					F
	S	0-9	10-19	20-29	30-39	40-49	50-59	60-69	70-79	80-89	90-100

Fig. 5 Past and New criticality matrices representation.

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this methodology is to align assets management to business value, not only from a hierarchical point of view, but also evaluating the network topology implications (considering the network graph). Network utilities are companies that provide essential services or products to customers where reputational impacts are higher than operational impacts. Consequently, infrastructure has to be analyzed with a risk-based methodology that considered these kinds of impacts in the risk assessment. Our methodology employs also graph coefficients in order to include survivability perspective, and it has been applied in several network utilities (electricity, gas, and telecom) of national importance in Spain. Software tools have been developed to manage criticality of their networks which have about 25,000 nodes per project application.

This methodology allows maintenance managers guiding the evolution of the life cycle of their infrastructure according to the business value conception, and at the same time to adapt their actions according to online data of in-service complex engineering assets. This makes this methodology especially suitable for supporting new challenging scenarios of maintenance management characterized for a high technological level, great interaction between assets and system and high rate of changing of demand and requirements of services. In addition, it will generate a great amount of data and information for the decision making.

This managerial tool allows structuring the maintenance department scorecard according to criticality levels. This facilitates graphic representations in different areas by level of criticality, delimiting the rank of assets encompassed by specific maintenance policies. For example, Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM), Root-Cause analysis (RCA) and RCM (Reliability Centered Maintenance) analysis can be suggested for critical assets; detailed Risk-Cost-Benefit analysis can be derived for semi-critical assets, and Run to Fail policies for non-critical. This relocates the maintenance efforts into more critical assets.

This methodology has been fully implemented in the telecom company that has provided the data used in this paper, with the followings results, improving network availability 0.73% (from 98.5% to 99.23%) in a planning horizon of two years, and with a 10% reduction of the maintenance overall budget in the

same period. The methodology has been applied at least in three network utilities companies of the oil&gas sector and two of electricity sector with similar results in all of them.

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REFERENCES

- [1] EN 13306:2010, Maintenance Terminology. European Standard. CEN (European Committee for Standardization), Brussels, 2010.
- [2] ISO 9001, Quality management systems—requirements. *International Standards for Business, Government and Society*, 2008.
- [3] DNP Murthy, A Atrens, JA Eccleston, "Strategic maintenance management". *Journal of Quality Maintenance Engineering* 8(4):287–305, 2002.
- [4] JG Janssens, L. Pintelon, A. Cotton, L. Gelders. "Development of a framework for the assessment of operation and maintenance (O&M) performance of urban water supply and sanitation". *Water Supply* 14(1):21–33, 1996.
- [5] A. Crespo, A. Sola, *Principles and framework of Asset Management*. AENOR, 2016.
- [6] ISO 55000:2013, Asset Management - Overview, principles and terminology.
- [7] K. El-Akruti, R. Dwight, T. Zhang. "The strategic role of Engineering Asset Management". *Int. J. Production Economics* 146: 227-239, 2013.
- [8] JF Gómez, A. Crespo, *Maintenance Management in Network Utilities: framework and practical implementation*. London: Springer-Verlag, 2012.
- [9] J. Zhou, N. Huang, X. Sun, K. Wang, H. Yang. "A new model of network cascading failures with dependent nodes". *Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium (RAMS)*, 2015.
- [10] P. Heegaard, K. Trivedi. "Network survivability modelling". *Computer Networks*, vol. 53, no. 8, pp. 1215-1234, 2009.
- [11] J. Sterbenz, D. Hutchison, E. Çetinkaya, A. Jabbar, J. Rohrer, M. Schöller and P. Smith, "Resilience and survivability in communication networks: Strategies, principles, and survey of disciplines", *Computer Networks*, vol. 54, no. 8, pp. 1245-1265, 2010.
- [12] F. Kamoun. "Toward best maintenance practices in communications network management". *International Journal of Network Management*, 15(5), 321–334, 2005.
- [13] J. Rubio-Loyola, G. Toscano-Pulido, M. Charalambides, M. Magaña-Aguilar, J. Serrat-Fernández, G. Pavlou and H. Galeana-Zapién. "Business-driven policy optimization for service management". *International Journal of Network Management*, 25(2), 113-140, 2015.
- [14] A. Crespo Márquez, *The Maintenance Management Framework. Models and Methods for Complex Systems Maintenance*. London: Springer Verlag UK, 2007.
- [15] JD. Campbell, A. Jardine, *Maintenance excellence*. New York: Marcel Dekker, 2001.
- [16] JH Saleh, KB Marais, "Reliability: How much is it worth? Beyond its estimation or prediction, the (net) present value of reliability". *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 91, 665–673, 2006.
- [17] EN 13269, Maintenance—guideline on preparation of maintenance contracts. *European Standard, CEN (European Committee for Standardization)*, Brussels, 2006.

- [18] A. Crespo, P. Moreu de León, A. Sola A, JF. Gómez. "Criticality Analysis for Maintenance Purposes: A Study for Complex In-service Engineering Assets". *Quality Reliability Engineering International*, 32 519–533 in Wiley Online Library, 2016.
- [19] FI Khan, M. Haddara, "Risk-based maintenance (RBM): a new approach for process plant inspection and maintenance". *Process Saf. Prog.* 23 (4): 252–265, 2003.
- [20] SJ Brown, IL May, "Risk-based hazardous protection and prevention by inspection and maintenance", *Trans. ASME J. Press. Ves. Technol.* 122: 362–367, 2000.
- [21] P. Weber, G. Medina-Oliva, C. Simon and B. Iung. (2012). "Overview on Bayesian networks applications for dependability, risk analysis and maintenance areas". *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 25(4), 671–682, 2012.
- [22] TR Moss, J. Woodhouse. "Criticality analysis revisited". *Quality and Reliability Engineering International*; 15:117–121, 1999.
- [23] US Department of Defense. Procedures for performing a failure mode and effects analysis, MIL-STD-1629A, 1977.
- [24] CE Palaez, JB Bowles. Using fuzzy logic for system criticality analysis, Proc. Reliability and Maintainability Symp., Anaheim, CA, January; 449–455, 1994.
- [25] A. Pillay, J. Wang. "Modified failure mode and effects analysis using approximate reasoning". *Reliability Engineering & System Safety* 2003; 79:69–85, 2003.
- [26] JF Gómez, A. Crespo, M. López-Campos, "Customer-oriented risk assessment in network utilities". *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 147, 72–83, 2016.
- [27] J. Sauve, M. Queiroz, A. Moura, C. Bartolini and M. Hickey. "Prioritizing information technology service investments under uncertainty". *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 8(3), 259–273, 2011.
- [28] A. Lima, J. Sauve, N. Souza. "Capturing the quality and business value of IT services using a business-driven model". *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 9 (4), pp. 421–432, 2012.
- [29] U. Franke. "Optimal IT service availability: Shorter outages, or fewer?". *IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management*, 9(1), 22–33, 2012.
- [30] R. Howes. "Improving the performance of Earned Value Analysis as a construction project management tool". *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, Vol. 7 Issue: 4, 399–411, 2000.
- [31] UNE 66178, Quality Management System. Guide for the management of process for improvement, 2004.
- [32] BG Dale, JJ Plunkett. Quality costing. Chapman Hall, London, 1991.
- [33] K. Al-Arfaj, K. Dahal, MN Azaiez. Maintenance cost models in deregulated power systems under opportunity costs. In: Proceedings of the IASTED international conference on energy and power systems, pp 284–291, 2007.
- [34] J. Amador, J. Domínguez. Application of geographical information systems to rural electrification with renewable energy sources. *Renew Energy* 30(12):1897–1912, 2005.
- [35] ME Beehler. Reliability centered maintenance for transmission systems. *IEEE Trans Power Del* 12(2):1023–1028, 1997.
- [36] RE Brown, HL Willis. The economics of aging infrastructure. *IEEE Power Energy Mag* 4(3):36–43, 2006.
- [37] DM Abraham, R. Wirahadikusumah, TJ Short, S. Shahbahrami. Optimization modelling for sewer network management. *J Constr Eng Manage* 124(5):402–410, 1998.
- [38] RE Brown, BG Humphrey. Asset management for transmission and distribution. *IEEE Power Energy Mag* 3(3):39–45, 2005.
- [39] RP Hoskins, AT Brint, G. Strbac. A structured approach to asset management within the electricity industry. *Utilities Policy* 7(4):221–232, 1999.
- [40] J. Woodhouse, Course of Reliability Centered Maintenance (RCM) – Section two: Failure Modes and Effects Analysis. The Woodhouse Partnership, England, 1996.
- [41] Zio. "Challenges in the vulnerability and risk analysis of critical infrastructures". *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 152: 137–150, 2016.
- [42] COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2008/114/EC. On the identification and designation of European critical infrastructures and the assessment of the need to improve their protection. Official Journal of the European Union, 2008.
- [43] S. Gupta, DR Lehman. Managing customers as investments: the strategic value of customers in the long run. Wharton School Publishing, New Jersey, 2005.
- [44] T. Wireman. Developing performance indicators for managing maintenance. New York: Industrial Press, 1998.
- [45] MIL-STD-882C Military Standard System Safety Program Requirements. Department of Defense, United States of America, 1993.
- [46] J. Goodman, Technical assistance research program (TARP). USA: US Office of consumer affairs study on complaint handling in America, 1986.
- [47] S. Keaveney. "Customer switching behaviour in service industries: an exploratory study". *J Mark* 59:71–82, 1995.
- [48] Customer-oriented risk assessment in network utilities. Juan F. Gómez Fernández, Adolfo Crespo Márquez, Mónica A. López-Campos. *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 147(2016)72–83 © ELSEVIER. ISSN: 0951-8320
- [49] Nowlan SF, Heap HF (1978) Reliability-centred maintenance. National Technical Information Service, US Department of Commerce, and Springfield Virgin
- [50] RF Knight, DJ Pretty. The impact of catastrophes on shareholder value. Oxford Executive Research Briefings, Templeton College, University of Oxford, 1997.
- [51] JP Rohrer, R. Naidu, JPG Sterbenz. Multipath at the Transport Layer: An End-to-End Resilience Mechanism. 9781-4244-3941-6/. IEEE, 2009.
- [52] JP Rohrer, JPG Sterbenz. "Predicting topology survivability using path diversity". Published in: Ultra Modern Telecommunications and Control Systems and Workshops (ICUMT), 2011 3rd International Congress on Conference. Page(s): 1 – 7. ISSN: 2157-0221. ISBN: 978-1-4577-0682-0. IEEE, 2011.
- [53] N. Meghanathan, "A computationally lightweight and localized centrality metric in lieu of betweenness centrality for complex network analysis", *Vietnam Journal of Computer Science*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 23–38, 2016.
- [54] M. Bevilacqua, M. Braglia. "The analytic hierarchy process applied to maintenance strategy selection". *Reliability Engineering and System Safety* 70: 71–83, 2000.
- [55] A. Molenaers, H. Baets, L. Pintelon, G. Waeyenbergh. "Criticality classification of spare parts: A case study". *Int. J. Production Economics* 140: 570–578, 2012.
- [56] MacGillivray BH, Sharp JV, Strutt JE, Hamilton PD, Pollard SJ. Benchmarking risk management within the international water utility sector Part I: design of a capability maturity methodology. *J Risk Res* 10(1):85–104, 2007
- [57] P. Vamvakas, E.E. Tsiropoulou, S. Papavassiliou. Dynamic Provider Selection & Power Resource Management in Competitive Wireless Communication Markets, in *Mobile Networks and Applications*, Springer, Volume 23, Issue 1, pp 86–99, February 2018.
- [58] C. Chi-Kin, W. Qian, C. Dah-Ming. On the viability of Paris metro pricing for communication and service networks. In: Proceedings IEEE INFOCOM, pp. 1–9, 2010.

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